

THE EFFECT OF VARYING N IN CLOZE PROCEDURE

Dr. Suvarna Shinde

Associate Professor & Head,
Dept. of English,
Arts and Commerce
College for Women, Deopur,
Dhule-424 005 (M.S.) INDIA.

Abstract

For assessment of overall proficiency of English language among the students of English language as second language learners the researcher had constructed Cloze Procedure test on a passage consisting of 868 words based on text book of English Prose and administered it on two groups of students at two different levels, one at an undergraduate level and another at a postgraduate level. At the undergraduate level 48 second year university undergraduate students doing a compulsory course in general English drawn from commerce faculty at Kamala College, Kolhapur (India) were selected. At post graduate level also 48 students doing their first year post graduation in English from Shivaji University, Kolhapur (India) were selected Both the groups consisted of male and female subjects with the mean age of 19.18 ± 1.45 year and 22.29 ± 0.89 year for undergraduate and post graduate students respectively. Four different tests were prepared deleting different number of words i.e. fifth, seventh, ninth & eleventh respectively and were given to both the groups. The results of the study showed that both the groups revealed almost the same results irrespective of the varying number of deleted words from Cloze Procedure.

Keywords: *Cloze Procedure, Deletion rates, Varying number, Language proficiency*

Introduction

Methodology

The test was administered to two groups of students at two different levels, one at an undergraduate level and another at postgraduate level. At the undergraduate level 48 second year university undergraduate doing a compulsory course in general English drawn from commerce faculty at Kamala College, Kolhapur were tested. At post graduate level also 48 students doing their first year post graduation in English from Shivaji University, Kolhapur were tested. The group consists of male and female subjects with the mean age of 19.18 ± 1.45 year and 22.29 ± 0.89 year for undergraduate and post graduate students respectively.

For assessment of proficiency of English language researcher had constructed an English passage 'Jawaharlal Nehru' written by his younger sister Krishna Hutheesing consisting 868 words

based on book of English Prose for Pre-University Class Somaiya Publications Pvt. Ltd. 1974. This was a prescribed text book for first Year University under graduates, doing compulsory course in general English at SNTD, Mumbai. The four deletion rates taken up for experimentation are: every fifth, seventh, ninth and eleventh word using the same prose passage four text formats, each comprising all the four close procedures differentially ordered are constructed. They are as follows:-

Formats	I	A	B	C	D
II	B	C	D	A	
III	C	D	A	B	
IV	D	A	B	C	
Procedure	A	Every fifth word deleted			
B	Every seventh word deleted				
C	Every ninth word deleted				
D	Every eleventh word deleted				

For each format the first and the last sentence were left intact. Contractions, Abbreviations and Hyphenated combinations were all regarded as single word. Blanks indicating the deletion of words were of ten spaces in length. Each procedure had twenty five items and thus each test format consisted of hundred items. Close procedures were differently ordered in different test formats in order to cancel out unevenness resulting from a particular order of the same assumption that this helps to ensure that all procedures get equal attention and chance of being attempted because in a long passage parts toward the end tend to get less of testee's attention.

While administering the cloze test at undergraduate level, the 48 students were divided into 4 groups each consisting of 12 subjects. Then they were given the four cloze test formats:- one test format to each group of 12 subjects. As the cloze test was unfamiliar to them, the nature of cloze test was explained. They were given two examples from the taught lessons of their text book. The passage selected for cloze test was unknown to them so it was read aloud in the class.

The summary of the passage was told briefly in Marathi their native language. The loud reading was intended to convey the overall content of the passage. The instructions for doing cloze tests were read aloud which were also given at the head of each test paper. It was pointed out that only one word should be used to fill each blank. The same cloze test was then administered to post graduate level. As they were the students of English language and literature nothing was explained to them about either the nature of cloze test or the passage. A full hour was given for the test to the subjects.

The test was scored by contextually acceptable word method. In order to be as objective and reasonable as possible all the alternative that appeared to be acceptable for those blanks where several alternative filled by the students were listed. Each set of alternative both for content words and

structure words were taken into account on the ground acceptability. And the response was either accepted or totally rejected.

To find out the statistical difference among all the selected groups of undergraduate and postgraduate students on selected English passage the researcher had applied analysis of variance as statistical tool which was done by SPSS version 20.

Results:

The results obtained from administration of four different tests to the undergraduate and postgraduate students are presented in table from 1 to 4. The table consists of descriptive statistical analysis of test score and analysis of variance to find out the statistical difference among the selected group of two different level .i.e. undergraduate and post graduate level.

Table-1: Descriptive Statistical Analysis Of Under Graduate Students

Test No.	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence interval for mean		Min.	Max.
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Test-1	12	39.0000	16.94376	4.89124	28.2345	49.7655	14.00	67.00
Test-2	12	36.6667	12.81571	3.69958	28.5240	44.8094	15.00	60.00
Test-3	12	30.7500	9.38204	2.70836	24.7889	36.7111	16.00	46.00
Test-4	12	28.9167	7.73961	2.23423	23.9992	33.8342	16.00	40.00
Total	48	33.8333	12.55852	1.81267	30.1867	37.4799	14.00	67.00

Table-1 shows the descriptive statistical analysis of score obtained from under graduate students on selected four different tests.

TabJe-2: Statistically Significant Difference of Mean of Under Graduate Students On Selected tests

Sr.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	820.833	3	273.611	1.826	1.156
Within Groups	6591.833	44	149.814		
Total	7412.667	47			

Table-2 depicts that, there were no statistically significant difference of mean found among the all the group on selected test as the calculated F value is 1.826 which is less then ($P>0.05$) to be significant.

Graph-I: Mean Representation of All the Tests Score of Undergraduate Students on Selected four tests

Table-3: Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Post Graduate Students on selected tests

Test No.	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence interval for mean		Min.	Max.
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Test-1	12	48.5833	20.76911	5.99553	35.3873	61.7794	30.00	90.00
Test-2	12	40.2500	8.19229	2.36491	35.0449	45.4551	30.00	55.00
Test-3	12	41.3333	16.00757	4.62099	31.1626	51.5041	19.00	68.00
Test-4	12	67.6667	9.18827	2.65242	41.8287	53.5046	36.00	66.00
Total	48	44.4583	14.50452	2.09355	40.2467	48.6700	19.00	90.00

Table-3 shows the descriptive statistical analysis of score obtained from post graduate students on selected four different tests

Table-4: Statistically Significant Difference of Mean of Post Graduate Students on Selected Tests

Sr.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	657.417	3	219.139	1.045	0.382
Within Groups	9230.500	44	209.784		
Total	9887.917	47			

Table-4 depicts that, there were no statistically significant difference of mean found among the group on selected test as the calculated F value is 1.045 which is less than ($P > 0.05$) to be significant.

Graph-2: Mean Representation of All the Tests Score of Post Graduate Students on selected tests**Discussion of findings:**

In the present scenarios teachers are looking forward for innovative method to make teaching easy and simple for the learner to understand subjects. In same way, Cloze procedure is one of the easiest and common methods used across the world to teach subjects, specially language. With this idea, researcher had constructed an English passage which consists of four different tests and implemented it to the two different groups at college as well as university level i.e. undergraduate and postgraduate students. Each group of students consists of 48 students which were further divided into groups of 12 students for every test.

On the ground of results, the researcher found that there were no statistically significant difference either in undergraduate students or postgraduate student in all the selected four tests of English passage in which different word was deleted after some gap of words respectively.

The choice of deletion rate in cloze procedure is a mechanical determinate of the amount of context around the blanks in terms of number of words. Empirical findings on the effects of varying N on performance generally agree in one respect and that is deletion rates from 5 to 12 keep results constant. One conclusion that can be drawn from this is that plus or minus five words from that blank is sufficient context for providing clues necessary to guess the cloze items. However a closer examination of this proposition revealed that clues may be located far away from blank sometimes many sentences before or after it. Also, the order of sentences which provide discourse clues is another factor. These together with several other intriguing and counterintuitive findings on this problem point towards the need for looking at the sensitivity of cloze items to immediate and remote contextual clues.

In another study Markhan (1985) while investigating the inter-sensitivity of cloze items supported the above findings. Along with him Bachman, (1978), Olier (1973), Cziko (1978) & Cleark (1979) maintain that cloze procedure is an objective and reliable measure of global comprehension.

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